

Study of solvation interaction in ethanol + octan-1-ol mixture[†]

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Solvation characteristic of 2,6-diphenyl-4-(2,4,6-triphenyl)-1-pyridinium phenolate, the indicator solute for the $E_T(30)$ scale of solvent polarity, has been studied as a function of solvent composition in the temperature range 293–313 K by monitoring the solvatochromic charge transfer band of the solute. The results, indicating preferential solvation of the solute by ethanol, have been analyzed in terms of a suitable model to get information about solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interaction. Viscosity and density of the solvent mixture as a function of solvent composition have been determined in the temperature range 283–313 K and the extent of non-ideality has also been estimated. It appears that the two procedures provide similar information about the nature of mutual interaction between the solvent molecules.

Mixed solvents are often used in chemistry to modify molecular environments in order to modulate processes such as chromatographic separation, organic synthesis, reaction kinetics and protein folding¹. Physical properties of binary solvent mixtures are often studied to get information about the mutual interaction between the solvent molecules². In an ideal situation it is assumed that the value of an extensive property (P) obeys simple additivity as given by the equation,

$$P_{12}(\text{ideal}) = x_1 P_1 + x_2 P_2 \quad (1)$$

where x denotes the mole fraction and the subscripts 1, 2 and 12 denote respectively the component solvents and their binary mixtures. The deviation from additivity rule, often expressed in terms of *excess* property [$\Delta P^E = P_{12} - P_{12}(\text{ideal})$], contains information of solvent-solvent interaction. Solvation of solute in a mixed binary solvent is another phenomenon, which depends on the mutual interaction of solvents. It is thus instructive to compare the nature of such interactions as obtained from studies involving two different procedures. It has been observed that the maximum energy of charge transfer (CT) transition in various solutes acts as a reporter of solvation interaction reflecting solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions at the microscopic level³⁻⁵. In the present study, we have studied the solvation of 2, 6-diphenyl-4-(2,4,6-triphenyl)-1-pyridinium phenolate, the indicator solute for the $E_T(30)$ scale of solvent polarity³, in ethanol + octan-1-ol binary mixture, by monitoring the longest wavelength charge transfer (CT) band of the solute as a function of solvent composition and temperature. Viscosity and molar volume of the solvent mixture have also been determined. The nature of solvent-solvent interaction,

as obtained from excess properties, has been compared with those obtained from solvation studies.

Results and discussion

Study of the binary solvent mixture :

Viscosity coefficient (η) and molar volume (V) of ethanol (1) + octan-1-ol (2) binary mixture are shown in the Table 1 as a function of solvent composition and temperature. It has been found that the excess volume, $\Delta V^E = V_{12} - (x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2)$ is slightly negative, but the magnitude is less than 1% of V . Viscosity coefficient for an ideal mixture is given by the relation,

$$\ln \eta_{12} = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 \quad (2)$$

The data obtained in the present investigation do not fit with eqn. (2), indicating non-ideal mixing of solvents. According to the Grunberg and Nissan⁷, the excess logarithmic viscosity is given by

$$\ln \eta^E = \ln \eta_{12} - (x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2) = x_1 x_2 d_{12} \quad (3)$$

where d_{12} is a parameter, which is regarded as a measure of the strength of interaction between unlike molecules. The excess logarithmic viscosity and estimated values of d_{12} are listed in Table 1. It appears that the value of d_{12} is concentration-dependent, indicating that the solvent mixture deviates from *regular solution behaviour*⁸. Values of excess energy of activation for viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\ddagger E}$) were calculated using equation,

$$\Delta G^{\ddagger E} = RT [\ln (\eta_{12} V_{12}) - x_1 \ln (\eta_1 V_1) - x_2 \ln (\eta_2 V_2)] \quad (4)$$

The results are given in Table 1. Fig. 1 shows the excess

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

properties, viz. $\ln \eta^E$ and ΔG^{*E} as a function of solvent composition. The composition dependence of ΔG^{*E} can be expressed by truncated Redlich-Kister relation⁹. Thus we have the following relations :

$$\Delta G^{*E}/x_1x_2 = 3.494 - 1.563(x_2 - x_1) + 3.357(x_2 - x_1)^2 - 4.326(x_2 - x_1)^3; T = 283 \text{ K} \quad (5a)$$

$$= 3.599 - 1.179(x_2 - x_1) + 3.089(x_2 - x_1)^2 - 3.925(x_2 - x_1)^3; T = 293 \text{ K} \quad (5b)$$

$$= 2.867 - 1.710(x_2 - x_1) + 2.084(x_2 - x_1)^2 - 2.822(x_2 - x_1)^3; T = 303 \text{ K} \quad (5c)$$

$$= 3.294 - 1.287(x_2 - x_1) + 2.487(x_2 - x_1)^2 - 1.643(x_2 - x_1)^3; T = 313 \text{ K} \quad (5d)$$

Plots of $\ln(\eta^V)$ vs $(1/T)$ for a particular solvent composition, gives a straight-line from which the value of ΔH^\ddagger , the enthalpy of activation for viscous flow, can be calculated. These are listed in Table 1, and shown as a function of solvent composition in Fig. 2. In an ideal situation one expects a linear dependence of ΔH^\ddagger on x over the entire range of composition. The ideal line is also shown in the Fig. 2. It may be noted positive deviation from ideality over the entire composition range has been observed. A positive value of ΔH^\ddagger indicates that the interaction between unlike molecules

Fig. 1. Plots of excess solvent property ($\ln \eta^E$ and ΔG^{*E}) as a function of solvent composition.

is less than that between like molecules².

Study of solvation :

Position of the CT band maximum shifts to the red with an increase in percentage of octan-1-ol. Increase in temperature also brings about a red-shift. The solvatochromism of the CT band is reversible and continuous; the bandwidth and shape do not change in the temperature range

Table 1. Different parameters for ethanol (1) + octan-1-ol (2) mixed binary solvents at various temperatures

Parameter	T	x ₁								
		0.00	0.20	0.31	0.40	0.54	0.73	0.86	0.92	1.00
η (mPa s)	283	13.28	9.82	7.94	6.92	5.47	3.84	2.68	2.35	1.47
	293	8.94	7.02	5.78	4.99	4.10	2.82	2.07	1.83	1.20
	303	6.82	5.05	4.14	3.61	3.04	2.14	1.62	1.44	1.00
	313	4.49	3.67	3.11	2.71	2.31	1.68	1.28	1.15	0.83
V (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	283	155.8	137.4	125.5	116.1	102.9	84.1	71.4	66.0	57.7
	293	156.9	137.5	126.4	117.1	103.8	84.9	71.9	66.2	58.4
	303	158.0	139.0	127.3	118.1	104.5	85.7	72.6	66.6	59.0
	313	159.1	139.8	128.2	119.1	105.4	86.4	73.2	67.2	59.6
ln η ^E	283	0.00	0.13	0.17	0.23	0.29	0.36	0.29	0.28	0.00
	293	0.00	0.15	0.18	0.22	0.22	0.31	0.26	0.25	0.00
	303	0.00	0.07	0.09	0.13	0.22	0.24	0.21	0.20	0.00
	313	0.00	0.13	0.15	0.17	0.23	0.24	0.19	0.19	0.00
d ₁₂	283	0.00	0.82	0.80	0.96	1.17	1.82	2.41	3.60	0.00
	293	0.00	0.95	0.84	0.92	0.88	1.56	2.19	3.21	0.00
	303	0.00	0.43	0.44	0.55	0.88	1.19	1.75	2.56	0.00
	313	0.00	0.81	0.72	0.71	1.92	1.32	1.60	2.29	0.00
ΔG ^{*E} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	283	0.00	0.52	0.67	0.79	1.02	1.03	0.84	0.73	0.00
	293	0.00	0.52	0.67	0.79	1.02	1.03	0.84	0.73	0.00
	303	0.00	0.33	0.46	0.59	0.83	0.86	0.70	0.59	0.00
	313	0.00	0.56	0.63	0.71	0.92	0.91	0.69	0.37	0.00
ΔG ^{*E} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-	28.7	26.8	25.5	25.4	23.4	22.2	19.8	19.4	14.7

Table 2. Maximum energy of transition of the betaine dye and preferential solvation parameters in ethanol (1) + octan-1-ol (2) mixed binary solvents at different temperatures

x_1	E_{12} (kcal mol ⁻¹)			$\delta_{s,1}$			$\ln K_{PS}$			ΔH_{PS} kJ mol ⁻¹
	293	303	313	293	303	313	293	303	313	
0.0	48.4	48.0	47.7	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	-	-	-
0.1	49.6	49.2	48.9	0.19	0.19	0.19	1.28	1.31	1.31	-1.2 ± 0.2
0.2	50.4	50.1	49.7	0.28	0.31	0.29	1.29	1.44	1.34	-1.9 ± 0.2
0.3	51.0	50.6	50.3	0.32	0.33	0.33	1.33	1.40	1.40	2.7 ± 0.3
0.4	51.4	50.9	50.6	0.31	0.31	0.31	1.32	1.29	1.29	1.2 ± 0.2
0.5	51.7	51.2	50.8	0.29	0.28	0.26	1.30	1.27	1.13	6.4 ± 1.1
0.6	51.8	51.3	50.9	0.21	0.20	0.18	1.04	1.01	0.86	6.8 ± 1.1
0.7	52.0	51.4	51.0	0.16	0.13	0.10	0.94	0.73	0.57	14.5 ± 1.8
0.8	52.1	51.5	51.1	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.62	0.38	0.19	16.1 ± 1.8
0.9	52.3	51.7	51.4	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.03	0.03	13.1 ± 1.8
1.0	52.6	52.1	51.8	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	-	-	-

 Fig. 2. Plot of ΔH^\ddagger as a function of solvent composition.

studied. The observed band-shifts were independent of the concentration of the solute in the range of concentration studied (10^{-3} – 10^{-5} M), indicating absence of solute-solute interaction.

Values of maximum transition energy (E_{12}) in the binary solvent mixture for different temperatures are listed in Table 2. For an ideal solvation behavior the value of transition energy in a binary solvent mixture would be given by the mole fraction average of transition energies (E_1 and E_2) of pure component solvents. Thus

$$E_{12}(\text{ideal}) = x_1 E_1 + x_2 E_2 \quad (6)$$

The observed values of E_{12} differ from E_{12} (ideal) values indicating that solvation is non-ideal. The dimensionless quantity, $\delta_{s,1} = \{[E_{12} - E_{12}(\text{ideal})]/(E_1 - E_2)\}$ data have been given in Table 2 and shown in Fig. 3. It may be noted that the excess solvent property and the excess solute property show almost similar composition dependence.

 Fig. 3. Plot of the dimensionless excess solute property, $\delta_{s,1}$ vs mole fraction of ethanol.

Deviation of an observed solute property from the ideal value is often described in terms of preferential solvation (PS) of the solute^{2,4,5,10–12}. It has been shown earlier that the quantity $\delta_{s,1}$ serves as an index of PS as follows^{4,13}:

$$\delta_{s,1} = x_1^L - x_1 \quad (7)$$

where x_1^L is the mole fraction of ethanol in the local region around the solute. The positive sign indicates that the solute is solvated preferentially by ethanol. The preference of ethanol over octan-1-ol is rationalizable in view of greater hydrogen bond donation ability of ethanol. Another parameter suitable for describing the temperature variation of PS characteristics is given by

$$K_{PS} = (x_1^L x_2) / (x_2^L x_1) \quad (8)$$

The parameter is related to the equilibrium,

where $\bar{1}$ and $\bar{2}$ represent component solvent molecules in the local region, while 1 and 2 represent those in the bulk. The value of K_{PS} can be calculated from the experimentally determined parameter as^{14,15}

$$K_{PS} = [(E_{12} - E_2) / (E_1 - E_{12})](x_2/x_1) \quad (10)$$

Table 2 lists the values of $\ln K_{PS}$. Positive value of $\ln K_{PS}$ indicates that the solute is preferentially solvated by the component 1, i.e. ethanol. According to the two-phase model solvation, where the solvent molecules are assumed to be distributed between the local and the bulk phase at equilibrium, the value of K_{PS} is determined by solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions and can be expressed as^{14,15}

$$kT \ln K_{PS} = [\varepsilon_{s2} - \varepsilon_{s1}] + [(N_1 - N_2)\varepsilon_{12} - (N_1^0 - N_2^0)\varepsilon_{12}^0 - N_1\varepsilon_{11} + N_1^0\varepsilon_{11}^0 + N_2\varepsilon_{22} - N_2^0\varepsilon_{22}^0 + (\varepsilon_{11} - \varepsilon_{22})/2 - (\varepsilon_{11}^0 - \varepsilon_{22}^0)/2] \quad (11)$$

here ε_{si} and ε_{ij} are energies of solute-i-solvent and i-solvent-j-solvent interactions, N_i is the number of i-solvent molecules, and the superscript (0) indicates the bulk phase. Terms in the first square bracket in the right-hand-side of eqn. (11) are the contribution of solute-solvent interaction, while the terms in the second square bracket are due to solvent non-ideality effect. When $\varepsilon_{11} = \varepsilon_{22} = \varepsilon_{12}$ and $\varepsilon_{ij} = \varepsilon_{ij}^0$, the term in the second square bracket becomes zero. Only under this condition (*pseudo-ideality*), will the value of $\ln K_{PS}$ be independent of the solvent composition. The experimental values of $\ln K_{PS}$ are however dependent on the solvent composition, indicating that solvent-solvent interaction plays a role in determining PS characteristics. To get an idea about the variation of $\ln K_{PS}$ with solvent composition, we proceeded as follows. Eqn. (11), with the assumption, $\varepsilon_{ij} = \varepsilon_{ij}^0$, meaning that interactions between solvent components in the local region are the same as than in the bulk, gives

$$kT \ln K_{PS} = (\varepsilon_{s2} - \varepsilon_{s1}) + 2(N_1 + N_2) \Delta\varepsilon_{12} [(x_1^L - x_1) + x_1(1 - (N_1 + N_1^0 + N_2 + N_2^0) / 2(N_1 + N_2))] + \text{constant} \quad (12)$$

where $\Delta\varepsilon_{12} = 2\varepsilon_{12} - \varepsilon_{11} - \varepsilon_{22}$. According to the eqn. (12), for a fixed solvent composition, a plot of $\ln K_{PS}$ vs $1/T$ would thus be linear. The values of ΔH_{PS} for the equilibrium (eqn. 9) obtained from the slope of $\ln K_{PS}$ vs $1/T$ plot for various systems are given in the Table 2. Values of ΔH_{PS} depend on solvent composition, as may be seen from the Fig. 4. ΔH_{PS} represents the heat change associated with replacement of one molecule of 2 in the local phase by one molecule of 1 in the bulk. As such, due to the existence of

Fig. 4. Plot of ΔH_{PS} vs the mole fraction of ethanol.

solvent-solvent interaction, the value is expected to depend on the bulk composition. The negative/positive value of ΔH_{PS} indicates that heat is liberated/absorbed in the process. From eqn. (12) we get,

$$-\Delta H_{PS}/N_A = (\varepsilon_{s2} - \varepsilon_{s1}) + 2(N_1 + N_2) \Delta\varepsilon_{12} [(x_1^L - x_1) + x_1(1 - (N_1 + N_1^0 + N_2 + N_2^0) / 2(N_1 + N_2))] \quad (13)$$

where $\Delta\varepsilon_{12} = 2\varepsilon_{12} - \varepsilon_{11} - \varepsilon_{22}$ and N_A is the Avogadro number.

In our experiment, solvent component 1 is the more polar component (e.g. in the E_T (30) scale) and thus it interacts with the solute to a greater extent. Considering that ε_{si} values are negative quantities, we have $(\varepsilon_{s2} - \varepsilon_{s1})$ as a positive quantity. In the present case, the first term in the square bracket in eqn. (13) is positive ($x_1^L > x_1$), but the second term is negative and largely compensates the positive term ($N_1 + N_1^0 + N_2 + N_2^0 \gg N_1 + N_2$). Thus a negative value of $\Delta\varepsilon_{12}$, would make ΔH_{PS} negative. A positive value of $\Delta\varepsilon_{12}$, on the other hand, would make ΔH_{PS} positive or slightly negative, depending on the relative magnitudes of solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions. In the present case, the values of ΔH_{PS} comes as positive quantities (slightly negative at the octan-1-ol end). This indicates that $\Delta\varepsilon_{12}$ is a positive term, which means that the interaction between the solvent molecules is relatively greater than that between unlike solvent molecules. Thus the present results indicate that the component solvent molecules repel each other in ethanol-octan-1-ol mixture.

Conclusion :

(i) Electronic spectroscopic study of the indicator dye for the E_T (30) scale may be used to investigate the preferential solvation characteristics of the solute as a function of

solvent and temperature. (ii) Besides the solute-solvent interaction, the mutual interaction between the solvent molecules also plays an important role in determining PS characteristics. (iii) Study of solvation in an ethanol + octan-1-ol mixture provides similar information about solvent-solvent interaction to that obtained from studies of viscosity of the solvent mixture at different temperatures.

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